

Self-made herbal oils and vegetables marinated in oil conceal health risks

BfR communication No 001/2016 of 4 January 2016

The production of vegetables such as peppers, chillis or aubergines marinated in oil is becoming more and more of a trend in private households. The same applies to the self-production of oils aromatised with garlic or fresh herbs. The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) was asked whether the risk of food poisoning caused by *Clostridium botulinum* toxins could exist with self-produced foods of this kind if they are prepared well in advance and kept in stock in the household over longer periods. After analysing the existing data from the available literature, the institute comes to the conclusion that the production process in private households cannot ensure that the growth of *Clostridium (C.) botulinum* and formation of botulinum toxin in the products can be generally avoided. For this reason, the BfR advises against the storage of self-made products, such as vegetables or herbs in oil, in private households. This applies in particular if the products are not sufficiently heated or used for cooking and roasting prior to consumption and are intended for the preparation of salads and other raw dishes.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/selbst-hergestellte-kraeuterole-und-in-oel-ingelegte-gemuese-bergen-gesundheitliche-risiken.pdf>